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Some Quantum-Theoretical Reflections on Cosmology

Abstract

Starting from the simplest non-trivial structures of quantum theory, a quantum cosmological model is developed in which abstract and absolute quantum information units (AQIs) form the basis of the global cosmic structure.

The state space of an AQI possesses the symmetry group $U(2)$, whose subgroup $SU(2)$ is geometrically interpreted as a three-dimensional sphere S^3 , serving as a model of space. Thus, a closed cosmic space arises directly from the structure of elementary quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom.

Starting from a set of global postulates motivated by quantum physics and without resorting to general relativity, relationships between the cosmic radius, the age of the universe, the energy content, and the number of AQIs are derived. This yields the equation of state $p = -\rho/3$. Within the framework of the Friedmann equations, this also leads to a linear cosmic expansion $R(t) = ct$. The model thus provides a quantum-theoretical justification for a homogeneous and isotropic cosmos without an additional inflationary phase.

Within the framework of the AQI model, various cosmological problems are discussed, including the horizon problem, the coincidence problem, and the observed rotation curves of galaxies. Furthermore, it is shown that the order of magnitude of the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy of black holes can be reconstructed from simple quantum-theoretical considerations.

General relativity is retained as a local macroscopic description of local inhomogeneities within a global quantum cosmological structure.

1 Introduction: Preliminary Quantum-Theoretical Considerations on Cosmology

In its established form, modern cosmology relies heavily on General Relativity (GR). This theory has proven extraordinarily successful in describing gravitational phenomena. At the same time, however, no generally accepted quantization of the complete General Theory of Relativity has been achieved for decades. This raises the question of whether the connection between quantum theory, gravity, and cosmology can also be explored in a different way: not through a subsequent quantization of gravity, but through a quantum-theoretical starting point for cosmology itself.

The approach pursued here therefore does not begin with classical fields, particles, or spacetime metrics, but with the simplest non-trivial structures of quantum theory.^{1, 2} These possess a two-dimensional complex state space.

They are referred to below as abstract and absolute quantum information units, or AQIs for short.

The AQIs are a further development of a proposal developed by Carl Friedrich von Weizsäcker.^{3, 4, 5, 6} As fundamental physical structures, the AQIs, unlike Weizsäcker's "primordial alternatives,"⁷ AQIs do not yet have any concrete meaning. However, AQIs are open to possible meanings that are only assigned in a concrete context.

To break through the almost inevitable automatic identification of "information" with "meaning," the *totality of AQIs* was designated with the rarely used term "*protyposis*" (Greek "the pre-formed").

The connections between such simple quantum structures and relativistic particles and their interactions have been demonstrated.^{8, 9, 10, 11}

The AQIs are used to formulate a model approach in which the global structure of the cosmos is to be understood from elementary quantum-theoretical premises.

The postulates of this model are not derivations from existing theories. They represent deliberate assumptions. However, their motivation does not lie in arbitrariness, but in the methodological principle of beginning physical descriptions with the simplest possible structures. The physical validity of such assumptions is demonstrated not primarily through their derivation from older theories, but through the simplicity, consistency, and explanatory power of their consequences.

The AQI approach is also reinforced by the observations highlighted by Richard Feynman¹² that the total energy of the cosmos can be considered zero and that the Hubble term corresponds to the inverse of the age of the universe, as well as by Albert Einstein's reflections.¹³

"One can give good reasons why reality cannot at all be represented by a continuous field. From quantum phenomena, it appears to follow with certainty that a finite system of finite energy can be completely described by a finite set of numbers (quantum numbers). This does not seem to be in accordance with a continuum theory and must lead to an attempt to find a purely algebraic theory for the description of reality. But nobody knows how to obtain the basis of such a theory."

These observations also support the AQI hypothesis, which views global cosmological evolution not only geometrically but also from a quantum-theoretical perspective.

Global empirical findings link the Hubble parameter H_0 to expansion. It has the dimension 1/time.

Fig. 1: Probability distribution for the dimensionless combination $H_0 t_0$.¹⁴

The observed value is close to one. This reinforced the idealization of a linear cosmic expansion $R(t) = ct$ in the AQI model.

The present approach differs from models that postulate additional fields or free parameters to explain individual cosmological observations. Rather, it asks whether central properties of the cosmos can be understood from a few global quantum-theoretical assumptions. These include, in particular, the identification of cosmic space with the state structure of an AQI, the assumption of a closed cosmos with vanishing total energy, and the assignment of a characteristic energy to an AQI according to the Planck relation.

These assumptions are necessarily open to criticism because they do not follow from the established standard model of cosmology. Precisely for this reason, they are clearly identified as postulates. What is decisive is not whether they can be directly derived from established theories, but whether a consistent cosmological model follows from them that describes known phenomena with fewer additional assumptions than in the Standard Model.

General Relativity is not discarded in the process. Rather, the aim is to show that its local validity for gravitational phenomena within the cosmos can be made plausible as a consequence of a global quantum cosmological structure. In this sense, it is not gravity that is placed at the beginning, but quantum theory.

The further structure of the work is therefore as follows: First, the fundamental postulates of the AQI model are formulated. Subsequently, it is shown how a closed cosmic space with the topology of a three-dimensional sphere can be motivated from the mathematical structure of an AQI. Building on this, the relationships between cosmic radius, age of the universe, AQI energy, energy density, and pressure are developed. Only then are the consequences for general relativity, for cosmological parameters, and for astrophysical phenomena examined.

The central result of the AQI model is that the equation of state $p = -\rho/3$ follows directly from the postulated quantum-theoretical scaling relations, without the need to invoke general relativity. Many of the cosmological consequences discussed in this article are derived from this relation. The connection to general relativity becomes clear from the fact that the equation of state $p = -\rho/3$ also leads to a linear expansion $R(t) = ct$ in the Friedmann equations.

Terminological Clarification

In the following, a distinction is made between the more specific terms *quantum mechanics*, *quantum field theory*, and *quantum information theory*, and the more broadly defined terms *quantum theory* and *quantum physics*.

Quantum mechanics is understood here as the standard formulation in which a fixed number of quantum particles is described in a given classical background or force field. This formulation is successful for many applications but presupposes the existence of particles as well as a classical space.

Quantum field theories extend this framework by describing systems with a variable number of particles and thus, in particular, enabling the creation and annihilation of quantum particles.

The *AQI hypothesis* is conceived as a *quantum information theory*. However, unlike conventional approaches, it does not assume that information is a property of particles or fields. These quantum-theoretical structures—which are the simplest in mathematical and physical terms—are interpreted as independent quantum systems in their own right, with their two-dimensional complex state space. The *AQI hypothesis* examines the primary properties independently of any specific connection to particles or fields.

In contrast, *quantum theory* or *quantum physics* in the broader sense refers to the general formal structure of quantum-physical descriptions, in particular state spaces, superpositions, and unitary transformations, without presupposing an interpretation in terms of particles or fields.

The present approach uses the term *quantum theory* in this more general sense. In particular, it does not assume a given number of particles or a classical space, but rather elementary quantum-theoretical structures, the abstract quantum information units (AQIs), from which both space and physical objects then emerge.

In this sense, quantum theory is understood as primary relative to the description of particles and fields.

2 Postulates for the Quantum Cosmology of AQIs

The aim of this section is the explicit formulation of the model's fundamental assumptions. These postulates define the conceptual basis for the subsequent derivation. They are not derived from theories of cosmology or quantum fields, but are motivated by the principle of reducing physical descriptions to the simplest quantum-theoretical structures.

2.1 Starting Point

The postulates define the conceptual foundation for the subsequent derivation. They are derived in part from observations, but not from the standard theories of cosmology or quantum fields. They are motivated by the principle of reducing physical descriptions to the minimal and structurally simplest quantum-theoretical assumptions in order to derive more complex phenomena from them.

The number N of AQIs provides a measure of the model's elementary quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom.

2.2 Postulates

P0 (elementary quantum structure)

The fundamental degrees of freedom of the cosmos are described by abstract quantum information units (AQIs), each characterized by a two-dimensional complex state space. The

norm-preserving symmetry group of the states is the group $U(2)$, the semidirect product of $U(1)$ and $SU(2)$.

P1 (cosmic space)

Cosmic space is identified, for modeling purposes, with the homogeneous space of the $SU(2)$ symmetry group of an AQI. It possesses the topology of a three-dimensional sphere S^3 .

P2 (total energy)

The cosmos is regarded as a closed system whose total energy vanishes at every instant:
 $E_{\text{total}} = 0$.

P3 (Cosmic Expansion)

The cosmic radius of curvature R of S^3 grows linearly with cosmic time t at the maximum speed for all real processes, c :

$$R(t) = ct.$$

This relationship is understood as a global description of the homogeneous and isotropic cosmos.

P4 (Energy scale of the AQIs)

Each AQI is assigned a characteristic energy that scales inversely with the cosmic age or the radius of curvature according to Planck's relation:

$$E_{AQI} \sim h/t \sim hc/R$$

This assignment defines the energy scale of the elementary degrees of freedom.

P5 (Dynamics of the degrees of freedom)

The number of AQIs grows monotonically with cosmic time. This increase describes cosmic evolution as the growth of available quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom.

2.3 Interpretation of the Postulates

Postulates P0 through P5 are deliberately formulated as minimal assumptions. Their physical justification arises from their structural simplicity and from the consequences that follow from them.

In particular, the identification of cosmic space with the state space of an AQI (P1) represents a conceptual generalization that establishes a direct connection between quantum theory and global cosmology.

Postulates P3 and P4 link the two physical constants h and c —which have been precisely determined experimentally and are of fundamental importance to quantum theory and special relativity—with the AQI model.

Postulate P3, which posits a fundamental role for the maximum speed in all real processes, does not originate from quantum theory. It allows special relativity and the role of the speed of light to be interpreted as a consequence of cosmic expansion.

The assignment of an energy to an AQI (P4) is not to be understood as a derived relationship, but rather as a definition of the model's energy scale. It is based on Planck's relation, but is deliberately introduced here as a postulate.

This definition is necessary to assign a physical dimension to the elementary degrees of freedom. Its justification follows from the consistency of the resulting cosmological relationships.

- The combination of these assumptions allows the cosmos to be described not as a system of predefined fields or particles, but as an evolving structure of quantum information.

The expansion of the cosmos is interpreted as an expression of an increase in degrees of freedom.

The validity of this approach is assessed below by the extent to which central properties of cosmological models arise from these few postulates.

The postulates P0 and P1 do not represent additional physical assumptions in the usual sense, but follow directly from the requirement to choose the simplest possible quantum-theoretical structures as a starting point.

A two-dimensional complex state space is the minimal possible non-trivial structure of quantum theory. The associated symmetry group $U(2)$ contains a three-dimensional compact manifold, $SU(2)$. The identification of this structure with cosmic space is therefore not an additional hypothesis, but the obvious geometric interpretation of the underlying quantum symmetry.

In this sense, P0 and P1 are not to be understood as arbitrary assumptions, but as direct consequences of the mathematical structure of the simplest quantum-theoretical systems.

3 Consequences of the Postulates

From the postulates formulated in Chapter 2, fundamental relationships between the cosmic radius, time, energy, degrees of freedom, as well as energy density and pressure can be directly derived. These relationships form the basis for the further physical interpretation of the model.

3.1 Cosmic Radius and Time Postulate

P3 directly implies the relationship between the cosmic radius of curvature and cosmic time:

$$R(t) = ct.$$

This equation describes the global evolution of a homogeneous and isotropic cosmos whose expansion proceeds at the maximum speed of real processes.

3.2 Number of Degrees of Freedom

According to Postulate P5, the number of AQIs grows with cosmic time. The states of an AQI correspond to a two-dimensional irreducible representation of $SU(2)$. As shown in Chapter 8.1, it follows from the geometric interpretation of an AQI as a globally extended structure, as well as from the existence of a minimal physically realizable length, the Planck length l_P , that the number of AQIs is proportional to the square of the cosmic radius:

$$N(t) \propto (R / l_P)^2.$$

Thus, using $R = ct$:

$$N(t) \propto t^2.$$

Cosmic evolution can thus be interpreted as the growth of quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom. The quadratic increase in the number of AQIs over linear cosmic time causes the

“time jumps” between one AQI and the next to become ever shorter. Time thus increasingly takes on a continuous, i.e., classical character.

According to the AQI hypothesis, the cosmos can be understood at any finite point in time as a structure consisting of a finite number of “quantum numbers.” Thus, Einstein’s search for “a purely algebraic theory” can be brought to fruition.

3.3 Energy of an AQI

From Postulate P4, the energy of a single AQI is given by:

$$E_{AQI} \sim h / t \sim h c / R.$$

This relationship reflects Planck’s connection between energy and characteristic extension and assigns each AQI an energy that decreases as the cosmic expansion increases.

3.4 Total Energy and Energy Density

The total energy of the AQIs is given by the sum over all degrees of freedom:

$$U(t) = N(t) E_{AQI}(t).$$

With $N \propto R^2$ and $E_{AQI} \propto 1/R$, it follows that:

$$U(t) \propto R.$$

The total energy of the material and energetic contents of the cosmos U thus grows linearly with the cosmic radius or with time.

The volume of a closed space with the topology of a three-dimensional sphere S^3 is given by:

$$V = 2\pi^2 R^3.$$

This yields the following for the energy density:

$$\rho(t) = U(t) / V(t) \propto R / R^3 \propto 1 / R^2.$$

3.5 Pressure and the Equation of State

The following relation is frequently used in thermodynamics but has a more general significance as an expression of *energy conservation in a homogeneous and isotropic system*:

$$dU + p dV = 0.$$

In the present context, this equation is not interpreted as a thermodynamic equation of state. In particular, neither temperature nor entropy is introduced. Rather, it describes the change in the energy content of a system under a change in volume at isotropic pressure.

Its application therefore does not require a thermodynamic equilibrium description, but follows solely from global energy conservation under the symmetry assumptions of homogeneity and isotropy.

In the present model, this relationship arises in connection with Postulate P2, according to which the total energy of the cosmos vanishes. The increase in the positive energy of the degrees of freedom must therefore be compensated by a corresponding contribution, which manifests itself in the form of an effective pressure term.

Using the previously derived scaling relations

$$U \propto R, V \propto R^3$$

it follows that

$$dU \propto dR, dV \propto 3 R^2 dR.$$

Substituting into the energy conservation equation yields

$$p \propto -1/R^2.$$

Comparing this with the energy density

$$\rho = U/V \propto 1/R^2,$$

we obtain the equation of state presented in Section 8.2

$$p = -\rho/3.$$

This relation represents a central result of the model. It follows directly from the postulates and the scaling relations derived from them, without additional assumptions regarding microscopic degrees of freedom, thermodynamic equilibria, or statistical distributions.

The form used here corresponds formally to the continuity equation of a homogeneous fluid in cosmology but is used without resorting to a thermodynamic interpretation.

3.6 Physical Interpretation

The equation of state $p = -\rho/3$, as a key result of the model, follows directly from the postulates, without additional assumptions about fields, particles, or cosmological constants.

A negative pressure of this form is compatible with cosmic expansion in general relativity. In particular, this relationship corresponds to a global dynamics in which the cosmic radius grows linearly with time. (Chapter 8.3)

Within this framework, the expansion of the cosmos can be interpreted as an expression of an increase in quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom. The increase in the number of AQIs leads to an increase in positive energy U , which is compensated by a global negative pressure p , so that the total energy of the cosmos vanishes according to Postulate P2.

4 Relationship to General Relativity

General Relativity (GR) describes gravitation as a geometric property of spacetime. In established cosmology, it is usually used as a fundamental starting point; matter and energy densities appear therein as sources of curvature.

The approach pursued here takes the opposite path. The starting point is not classical fields or spacetime metrics, but quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom in the form of AQIs. It is only from their global structure that energy density and pressure arise.

The question is therefore not how general relativity can be quantized, but whether its cosmological solutions can be understood as a macroscopic description of a fundamental quantum-theoretical structure.

Postulates P1 through P5 do not presuppose general relativity. However, as will be shown below, they lead to a cosmology that is a solution to general relativity:

For a homogeneous and isotropic cosmos, the Einstein equations lead to the Friedmann equations

$$(R'/R)^2 = 8\pi G \rho/3 - k/R^2,$$

with $k=1$ for a spherical space, as well as

$$R''/R = -(4\pi G/3)(\rho + 3p).$$

In the AQI model, the state equation follows directly from the postulates:

$$p = -\rho/3$$

Thus, the term $\rho+3p$ vanishes in the second Friedmann equation, so that:

$$R'' = 0$$

The expansion of the cosmos thus proceeds at a constant speed. In general, this yields

$$R(t) = At+B$$

If the origin is chosen such that at the beginning of cosmic evolution there is a minimal length on the order of the Planck length, it follows that

$$R(t) = ct + l_{Pl}$$

and for large times, approximately

$$R(t) \approx ct$$

Thus, the equations of state of the AQIs and the cosmological model follow from postulates P0 through P5. This cosmological model is a solution to GR that was not presupposed. If one does not assume the postulates, but only the equations of state of the AQIs and GR, then the cosmological model of an S^3 expanding at the speed of light is again obtained.

It should be noted that General Relativity retains its local validity completely in the AQI model. The Einstein equations are not modified. Rather, the cosmological dynamics arise from a different physical interpretation of the sources of energy density and pressure.

Gravity thus appears not as a fundamentally presupposed interaction, but as a macroscopic geometric response to the underlying quantum-theoretical structure of the cosmos.

In this sense, the General Theory of Relativity could be understood similarly to continuum mechanics in classical physics: as an extremely successful effective description of collective degrees of freedom, whose microscopic basis, however, is of a quantum-theoretical nature.

The dimensionless combination $H_0 t_0$ is close to the value one in observations. This suggests interpreting the Hubble parameter not primarily as a constant, but as an inverse cosmic time scale. In the AQI model, this observation is idealized by the global relation $R(t) = ct$.

5 Cosmological Consequences of the AQI Model

The preceding relations yield far-reaching consequences for central problems in modern cosmology. Of particular significance is that the entire dynamics follows from a few global quantum-theoretical postulates, without the need to introduce additional fields or free cosmological parameters.

5.1 Horizon Problem

The cosmic microwave background exhibits remarkable homogeneity and isotropy over very large angular scales. In the standard model, this gives rise to the so-called horizon problem, since, according to conventional calculations, regions far apart could never have been causally connected.

In the Λ CDM model, this problem is addressed by a very early phase of exponential expansion—inflation. However, this requires the postulation of additional fields and potentials.

In the AQI model, on the other hand, a linear expansion is postulated

$$R(t) = ct$$

With such dynamics, the causal horizon grows proportionally to cosmic time. Regions which appear far apart today, could therefore have been causally coupled in the early cosmos. The observed homogeneity thus arises without the introduction of an inflationary field.

In this context, inflation does not appear to be a necessary fundamental phase, but possibly an indication that the underlying cosmological dynamics are incompletely described in the standard model.

5.2 Coincidence Problem

One of the most striking observations in modern cosmology is that the present-day energy density of a cosmological term is of the same order of magnitude as the energy densities of matter plus radiation.

In the Standard Model, this appears to be an unexplained coincidence¹⁵, since the respective contributions evolve differently with cosmic expansion.

In the AQI model, however, the total energy density arises from the shared structure of the AQIs. The various contributions—matter, radiation, and the effective cosmological term—are therefore not independent of one another but structurally coupled.

As shown in Chapter 8.4, it follows that the effective cosmological term is of the same order of magnitude as the contributions from the energy densities of matter ρ_M and radiation ρ_L :

$$(\rho_M + \rho_L)/2 \leq \Lambda \leq \rho_M + \rho_L$$

Thus, the coincidence problem ceases to be a separate cosmological puzzle.

5.3 Rotation Curves of Galaxies

The observed flat rotation curves of galaxies are usually explained in the standard model by an additional dark matter component. However, several papers by Matos, Guzmán, and colleagues^{16, 17, 18, 19} show, however, that corresponding rotation profiles within general relativity can already result from an equation of state of the form $p = -\rho/3$.

The approach by Matos and Guzmán was discussed by Kiselev²⁰, who confirms the effects for $p = -\rho/3$, which are otherwise attributed to hypothetical cold dark matter (CDM).

Rahaman et al.^{21, 22} investigated possible cosmological consequences of the observed rotation curves within the framework of GR. These authors start from the flat rotation curves of galaxies and find the equation of state $p = -\rho/3$ as a cosmological consequence.

It is noteworthy that no modification of the Einstein equations is necessary. Rather, the observed effects arise from a specific global structure of pressure and energy density.

Görnitz and Schomäcker²³ investigated the interesting role of rotating central black holes. To describe the embedding of a rotating black hole in an expanding closed universe, Vaidya specified a suitable form of the Kerr metric within the framework of general relativity.²⁴

The fact that the equation of state $p = -\rho/3$ applies to the cosmos on a large scale does not immediately allow us to conclude that this must also hold true in the vicinity of the black hole. There, the generally homogeneous and isotropic metric transitions into a cylindrically symmetric metric around the black hole's axis of rotation. The three identical components of the pressure merge into one pointing in the direction of the axis and two identical ones pointing radially toward the plane of rotation.

Calculations using this metric for a rotating black hole in an expanding S^3 cosmos can be found in Görnitz and Schomäcker.²⁵ In the model calculations, it appears that the AQI state equation is preserved in the rotation plane almost all the way to the horizon.

Fig. 2: Behavior of the energy density and the pressure components in the vicinity of a rotating black hole. In the rotation plane, the equation of state $p \approx -\rho/3$ is preserved up to close to the event horizon.

In the figure, the numerical calculations show that in the plane of rotation of the black hole, the equation of state $p = -\rho/3$ remains valid up to close to the event horizon. In the plane of rotation of the black hole, the stars that exhibit the peculiar rotational behavior orbit around the center.

This suggests a possible explanation of the galactic rotation curves without additional hypothetical particle components.

In the direction of the rotation axis, however, a positive pressure is observed. This local positive pressure, in the cosmic vicinity of the negative pressure, can contribute a gravitational component to the jet structures around active black holes, which have so far been explained primarily by electromagnetic effects.

5.4 Gravitational Lensing

Observations of gravitational lensing point to additional gravitationally effective structures that cannot be fully explained by visible matter. In the AQI model, local condensations of extended AQI structures could contribute to such gravitational effects without the need to introduce additional particle components.

5.5 Interpretation

The examples presented show that a number of central cosmological problems can be addressed within the framework of a few global quantum-theoretical postulates. The aim is not to reproduce all astrophysical details with quantitative precision. Rather, the strength of the approach lies in the fact that various phenomena—the horizon problem, the coincidence problem, the cosmological term, rotation curves, and gravitational lensing—become understandable on a common structural basis. The AQI model thus suggests reducing the total number of independent assumptions.

6 Black Holes in the AQI -Model

Black holes mark the area where the tension between quantum theory and general relativity is particularly evident. While general relativity predicts event horizons and singularities, the AQI-hypothesis requires a description of physical states through finite degrees of freedom.

In the AQI model, black holes are therefore not primarily understood as classical geometric singularities, but as highly condensed configurations of quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom.

For a black hole, the classical relationship between radius and energy holds ^{26, 27}

$$r_{BH} = 2G E_{BH} / c^4$$

In the AQI model, the energy of a black hole E_{BH} is given by the sum of the energies of its elementary degrees of freedom:

$$E_{BH} = n_{BH} E_{AQI}$$

Since each AQI is assigned an energy proportional to $1/R$, the mass of a black hole can be interpreted as the collective state of many AQIs.

It is noteworthy that the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy can be reconstructed in this framework in a very simple manner. (Chapter 8.5) Entropy does not appear here as an additional fundamental quantity, but as a measure of the number of possible internal configurations of the AQIs.

Thus, the well-known area proportionality of entropy receives a direct quantum-theoretical interpretation.

At the same time, the classical Schwarzschild singularity disappears. (Chapter 8.6) In the AQI model, the interior of a black hole is not understood as a point of infinite density, but as a stationary closed space with finite curvature.

The classical singularity thus appears as a consequence of the limitations of a purely classical description.

The so-called *information paradox* also receives a different interpretation: Information is not lost; rather, complex macroscopic states are decomposed into elementary quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom upon crossing the horizon. This shifts the focus: it is not the conservation of meaning that is fundamental, but the conservation of quantum-theoretical degrees of freedom. The original meanings that may have been assigned to macroscopic structures can be lost in the process without altering the underlying set of AQIs. It remains to be seen how this process opens up a possible interpretation of the *firewall problem*.

With the AQI model, black holes are not to be regarded as pathological special cases of gravity, but as natural consequences of a quantum-theoretical cosmology. The description of black holes suggests that their essential properties—energy, entropy, and information behavior—can be understood as consequences of the underlying quantum-theoretical structure.

In particular, entropy does not appear as an additional quantity, but as a direct consequence of the number of possible configurations of AQIs within a black hole. Likewise, the classical singularity is replaced by a structure grounded in quantum theory.

7 What happens to Dark Matter, Dark Energy, and the Cosmological Term.

Current standard cosmology describes various astrophysical observations using additional components such as dark matter, dark energy, and a cosmological term Λ . In the AQI model, the question arises as to whether these phenomena can be understood, at least in part, based on the global equation of state $p = -\rho/3$ and its local gravitational effects.

The AQI framework remains compatible with the existence of additional forms of matter. However, it reduces the need to explain the observed phenomena exclusively through new types of particles.

In the AQI model, dark matter, dark energy, and an effective cosmological term do not appear as independent additional assumptions, but rather as different aspects of the same global quantum cosmological structure. Crucially, several previously independent cosmological problems can be traced back to a common structural cause.

8 Mathematical Appendix

8.1 Symmetry Structure of AQIs and Representation Theory of SU(2)

The elementary degrees of freedom of the present model are described by AQIs. The state space of an AQI is the two-dimensional complex vector space C^2 . The symmetry group that leaves the square of the scalar product invariant is the unitary group U(2). This decomposes into the subgroups U(1) and SU(2):

$$U(2) \cong U(1) \times SU(2).$$

The SU(2) group forms a three-dimensional compact manifold that is topologically equivalent to the three-dimensional surface S^3 of a four-dimensional sphere. In the AQI model, this structure is identified as model for the cosmic space. The remaining U(1) freedom describes a global phase rotation $e^{-i\varphi}$.

Within a purely unitary description, this phase has a cyclic character. If it is formally extended to a non-unitary parameter, $\varphi \rightarrow it$, it can be interpreted as a growing time parameter:

$$e^{-i\varphi} \rightarrow e^t.$$

This extension has a heuristic character. It motivates the introduction of a directed cosmic time from the structure of the fundamental quantum symmetry.

The irreducible representations of SU(2) play a central role in the spatial structure of the model. The regular representation of the group acts on the Hilbert space of square-integrable functions over the group itself:

$$L^2(SU(2)) = L^2(S^3).$$

The two-dimensional representation of a single AQI corresponds to functions with wavelengths on the order of the cosmic radius of curvature. A single AQI therefore has no local spatial assignment, but rather represents a structure extending across the entire cosmic space.

Only tensor products of many AQIs enable higher-dimensional irreducible representations with shorter wavelengths and thus the formation of localized structures.

The tensor product of N fundamental two-dimensional representations decomposes as follows

$$\left({}^{(2)}D \right)^{\otimes N} = \sum_{l=0}^{l=N/2} f(l) {}^{(2l+1)}D$$

The multiplicities $f(l)$ are given by

$$f(l) = \frac{N! (2l + 1)}{\left(\frac{N}{2} + l + 1\right)! \left(\frac{N}{2} - l\right)!}$$

Representations with larger l correspond to shorter wavelengths on S^3 .

Numerical studies show that the multiplicities initially vary relatively slowly and then decay exponentially starting from a characteristic range. This transition occurs at

$$l \approx 2 \sqrt{N}.$$

The corresponding minimum physically relevant wavelength is identified in the model with the Planck length. This yields

$$l_{Pl} \approx R/2 \sqrt{N}$$

From this follows the relation

$$R = 2 l_{Pl} \sqrt{N}.$$

Fig. 3: Decomposition of the tensor product of $N = 900$ two-dimensional representations of $SU(2)$ into irreducible representations. Shown are, in a doubly logarithmic plot, the multiplicities as a function of the parameter l (see text). The multiplicities decrease exponentially after $l = 2 \sqrt{N} = 60$, which can be associated with a smallest wavelength $l_{Pl} = R / 2\sqrt{N}$.²⁸

The magnitude of $f(l)$ changes relatively little in the interval from $l = 0$ to a value of $l = 2 \sqrt{N}$. Then an exponential decrease occurs.

The argument is heuristic rather than rigorous. It should therefore be understood as a physically motivated scaling relation rather than a strict derivation. It serves as a representation-theoretical motivation for the fact that in a cosmos with a finite AQI number, a minimal physically relevant length scale appears.

8.2 Relationship between AQI number, cosmic radius, and energy

From the representation-theoretic relationship

$$R = 2 l_{Pl} \sqrt{N}$$

it immediately follows that

$$N = R^2/4 l_{Pl}^2.$$

With the postulate of linear cosmic expansion $R = ct$ we obtain

$$N(t) = c^2 t^2/4 l_{Pl}^2.$$

The number of AQIs thus grows proportionally to the square of the cosmic age.

The energy of a single AQI is determined by the postulate

$$E_{AQI} \sim h / t .$$

Using $R = ct$, it follows equivalently that

$$E_{AQI} \sim hc/R.$$

If the wavelength of an AQI is identified with the order of magnitude of the cosmic radius,

$$\lambda \approx 2\pi R,$$

then more precisely

$$E_{AQI} = hc/2\pi R$$

The total energy of the cosmic content is given by the sum over all AQIs:

$$U = N E_{AQI}.$$

With

$$N = R^2/4 l_{Pl}^2$$

it follows that

$$U \propto R,$$

more precisely

$$U = (R^2/4 l_{Pl}^2) (hc/2\pi R) = R hc /2\pi 4 l_{Pl}^2$$

The total energy thus increases linearly with the cosmic radius or with the cosmic age.

For a three-dimensional sphere, the volume is

$$V = 2\pi^2 R^3$$

This yields the energy density

$$\rho = U/V \propto 1/R^2,$$

more precisely

$$\rho = (R hc /2\pi 4 l_{Pl}^2) / 2\pi^2 R^3 = hc / 16 l_{Pl}^2 \pi^3 R^2$$

Applying global energy conservation to a homogeneous and isotropic system yields the relationship

$$dU + p dV = 0$$

This equation is not interpreted here as a thermodynamic equation of state. In particular, neither temperature nor entropy is assumed. Rather, it describes the change in the energy content of a homogeneous system under isotropic volume change.

With

$$U = hc R / 8\pi l_P^2$$

we obtain:

$$dU/dR = hc / 8\pi l_P^2.$$

With $V = 2\pi^2 R^3$ we obtain:

$$dV/dR = 6\pi^2 R^2.$$

So:

$$p = - (dU/dR) / (dV/dR) = -(hc / 8\pi l_P^2) \cdot (1 / 6\pi^2 R^2).$$

Thus:

$$p = -hc / 48\pi^3 l_P^2 R^2.$$

Comparison with

$$\rho = hc / 16\pi^3 l_P^2 R^2$$

yields:

$$p = -\rho/3.$$

8.3 Friedmann Equations

For a homogeneous and isotropic cosmos, the following holds:

$$(R' / R)^2 = (8\pi G / 3) \rho - k / R^2,$$

$$R'' / R = -(4\pi G/3) (\rho + 3p).$$

where $R(t)$ describes the cosmic scale factor and k characterizes the spatial curvature. In the spherical case, $k = 1$.

With $p = -\rho/3$ it follows that:

$$R'' = 0.$$

Thus:

$$R(t) = At + B.$$

If the origin is chosen such that $R(0) = l_{Pl}$, then it follows:

$$R(t) = At + l_{Pl}.$$

With the postulated maximum speed $A = c$, we obtain:

$$R(t) = ct + l_{Pl}.$$

8.4 Λ -Term and Coincidence Relation

Not all AQIs form matter or light quanta. The components of their energy densities are denoted by ρ_M and ρ_L , and that of an effective cosmological term by ρ_Λ .

The sum ρ_0 of the three terms forms a summand of the total energy density ρ_{total} with the same equation of state as ρ_{total} .

$$\rho_0 = \rho_M + \rho_L + \rho_\Lambda \quad \text{with} \quad p_0 = -\rho_0/3.$$

For matter (as pressureless dust), the equation of state is $p_M = 0$, for radiation $p_L = +\rho_L/3$, and for a cosmological term $p_\Lambda = -\rho_\Lambda$.

This yields the following distributions of energy densities

$$\rho_0 = \rho_M + \rho_L + \rho_\Lambda$$

and of the pressures

$$-\rho_0/3 = +\rho_L/3 - \rho_\Lambda \quad \text{or} \quad \rho_0 = -\rho_L + 3\rho_\Lambda$$

Setting these two equations equal yields:

$$\rho_M + 2\rho_L = 2\rho_\Lambda \quad \text{or} \quad \rho_\Lambda = \rho_M/2 + \rho_L$$

With

$$\omega = \rho_M/\rho_L$$

we obtain

$$\rho_M = \omega \rho_L \quad \text{with} \quad 0 \leq \omega \leq \infty.$$

For ρ_0 , we have

$$\rho_0 = 3 \rho_M/2 + 2 \rho_L = (2 + 3 \omega/2) \rho_L$$

and finally

$$\rho_L = \rho_0 \cdot 2 / (3 \omega + 4)$$

$$\rho_M = \rho_0 \cdot 2 \omega / (3 \omega + 4)$$

and thus

$$(\rho_L + \rho_M) = 2 \rho_0 (1 + \omega) / (3\omega + 4)$$

For the Λ term

$$\rho_\Lambda = \rho_0 (2 + \omega) / (3\omega + 4)$$

it follows that, for $0 \leq \omega \leq \infty$

$$\rho_0/3 \leq \rho_\Lambda \leq \rho_0/2.$$

Furthermore,

$$\rho_0/2 \leq \rho_M + \rho_L \leq 2 \rho_0/3 \quad \text{or} \quad \rho_0/4 \leq (\rho_M + \rho_L)/2 \leq \rho_0/3$$

The bounds for the Λ term provide the solution to the coincidence problem:

$$(\rho_M + \rho_L)/2 \leq \rho_0/3 \leq \rho_\Lambda \leq \rho_0/2 \leq \rho_M + \rho_L \leq 2 \rho_0/3$$

thus

$$(\rho_M + \rho_L)/2 \leq \rho_\Lambda \leq \rho_M + \rho_L$$

In the AQI model, the effective Λ -term does not emerge as an independent fundamental constant, but as a necessary consequence of the decomposition of the energy-density-pressure tensor. Consequently, its order of magnitude remains automatically coupled to the energy densities of matter and radiation.

8.5 Entropy of a Black Hole

For a black hole with radius r_{BH} and energy E_{BH} , the classical Schwarzschild relation between the Schwarzschild radius r_{BH} and mass holds:

$$r_{BH} = 2 G M_{BH}/c^2 = 2 G E_{BH}/c^4$$

The surface area of the event horizon A (Black Hole Area) is given by

$$A = 16\pi M_{BH}^2 = 4\pi r_{BH}^2$$

According to Bekenstein and Hawking²⁹, the entropy S_{BH} of such a black hole is:

$$S_{BH} = \frac{k_B 2\pi A c^3}{4 G h} = \frac{k_B 2\pi (4\pi r_{BH}^2) c^3}{4 G h}$$

If the temperature is measured in units of energy, then $k_B = 1$ can be set.

$$S_{BH} = \frac{\pi A c^3}{2 G h} = \frac{(4\pi r_{BH}^2) \pi c^3}{2 G h}$$

We will now show how, through a nearly elementary consideration using the AQIs, the order of magnitude of the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy of a black hole can be derived.³⁰

To generate the mass of the black hole via the energy of the AQIs, the number n_{BH} of AQIs is required. Each AQI is assigned an energy $E_{AQI} = h c/R$:

$$M_{BH} = E_{BH}/c^2 = n_{BH} E_{AQI}/c^2 = n_{BH} h c/2\pi R c^2$$

From the representation theory of $SU(2)$, it follows that s AQIs in a cosmos with radius R can generate structures with wavelengths of an extent on the order of R/s . To form a localized structure with a wavelength of $2\pi r_{BH}$ in a cosmos with radius R , s_{BH} AQIs are required.

$$2\pi r_{BH} = R/s_{BH}$$

or

$$s_{BH} = R/2\pi r_{BH}$$

The total number n_{BH} of AQIs constitutes the mass of the black hole:

$$E_{BH} = n_{BH} E_{AQI} = n_{BH} h c/2\pi R$$

The number n_{BH} is factored into

$$n_{BH} = s_{BH} z_{BH}$$

The total number n_{BH} of AQIs that coalesce to form the black hole can thus be divided into information that is, in principle, accessible, and a portion that is inaccessible—that is, entropy. In this context, s_{BH} describes the number of AQIs required to localize a structure with the characteristic size r_{BH} within a cosmos of radius R . The factor z_{BH} counts the possible internal configurations of these localized states and is therefore identified with the entropy of the black hole.

Such a relationship can only make sense in a closed cosmos. It cannot be formulated in a flat cosmos.

The extent of the s_{BH} structures is such that they can be trapped within the black hole's event horizon. These s_{BH} structures would now form "fundamental wave functions within the black hole," analogous to the AQIs as "fundamental wave functions in the cosmos."

Thus, S_{BH} corresponds to the amount of information about the size and location of the black hole in the vast cosmos that can, in principle, be determined from the outside. S_{BH} contributes one term to the mass (or rest energy) of the black hole, and z_{BH} contributes the other.

- S_{BH} refers to externally distinguishable degrees of freedom.

The second factor z_{BH} describes the number of inaccessible internal states available to the various S_{BH} structures.

- z_{BH} corresponds to the entropy of the black hole.

This provides the second factor for the mass.

$$n_{BH} = S_{BH} \cdot z_{BH} = z_{BH} R / 2\pi r_{BH}$$

In the AQI model, it is assumed that the same fundamental relation between energy, extent, and quantization applies to cosmological spaces and black holes. The Bekenstein relation, which follows from GR, is generally supposed to apply to the extent of a closed space if the closure behind a horizon is caused by the energy contained within it.

The two expressions for the energy of the black hole from general relativity and via the AQIs of the protyposis should be equal.

From GR with $A = 4\pi r_{BH}^2 = 16\pi (G M/c^2)^2$ it follows

$$r_{BH}^2 = 4 (G M_{BH}/c^2)^2 = 4 (G E_{BH}/c^4)^2$$

and thus

$$r_{BH} = 2 G E_{BH}/c^4 \quad \Rightarrow \quad E_{BH} = r_{BH} c^4 / 2 G$$

From AQI cosmology it follows

$$E_{BH} = n_{BH} E_{AQI} = (z_{BH} R / 2\pi r_{BH}) (h c / 2\pi R) = h c z_{BH} / 2\pi 2\pi r_{BH}$$

If both results for the energy are to agree, we obtain

$$r_{BH} c^4 / 2 G = h c z_{BH} / 2\pi 2\pi r_{BH}$$

and further

$$z_{BH} = 2\pi 2\pi r_{BH}^2 c^3 / 2 G h$$

The Bekenstein-Hawking entropy of a black hole is

$$S_{BH} = 4\pi^2 r_{BH}^2 c^3 / (2G h)$$

Thus,

$$z_{BH} = S_{BH}$$

The AQI model reproduces the area proportionality as well as the order of magnitude of the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy.

8.6 The Interior of a Black Hole

Quantum theory demonstrates, via Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, that the ground state of a quantized system is altered by spatial boundaries. The vacuum state within a closed region therefore differs fundamentally from the vacuum state of the surrounding space.

Black holes represent the most extreme form of such a closed region. This suggests that, from a quantum theoretical perspective, the interior of a black hole should not simply be treated as

an analytical continuation of the external space. Thus, the AQI hypothesis shows that the interior of a black hole can be interpreted as a steady-state FLRW universe ³¹:

We consider a static spherically symmetric metric of the form

$$ds^2 = e^{2A} dt^2 - e^{2B} dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)$$

Due to the spherical symmetry and the static nature (based on Birkhoff's theorem), A and B are merely functions of r and not of t , θ , and ϕ . For the exterior space $R_{BH} < r < \infty$, we choose $A = \frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - R_{BH}/r)$ and $B = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - R_{BH}/r)$. Thus, R_{BH} becomes the horizon of a Schwarzschild metric:

$$ds^2 = (1 - R_{BH}/r) dt^2 - [(1 - R_{BH}/r)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)]$$

We seek, for $0 < r < R_{BH}$, a regular spherically symmetric interior solution with finite curvature and homogeneous energy density. A minimal possible choice is given by $A = 0$ and $B = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(1 - r^2/R_{BH}^2)$. We obtain

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - [(1 - r^2/R_{BH}^2)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)]$$

Using Einstein's field equations with $\kappa = 8\pi G/c^2$, the non-zero components of the energy-density-pressure tensor for an ideal fluid are

$$\rho = 3/(\kappa R_{BH}^2) \quad \text{as well as} \quad p = -1/(\kappa R_{BH}^2)$$

The total mass

$$2M = \kappa \int_0^{R_{BH}} \rho r^2 dr = R_{BH}$$

shows that R_{BH} can be interpreted as the Schwarzschild radius of the black hole. In new coordinates $r_{in} = r/R_{BH}$, the line element takes the form

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - R_{BH}^2 [(1 - r_{in}^2)^{-1} dr_{in}^2 + r_{in}^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2)]$$

as a stationary FLRW universe with curvature radius R_{BH} .

The classical Schwarzschild singularity no longer appears in this description. Instead of a divergent energy density, a regular interior with finite curvature results.

9 Limitations of the Model

The AQI model is primarily examined here in terms of its global quantum cosmological significance. The focus is on the relationships between fundamental structures of quantum theory, cosmic dynamics, and gravitational phenomena.

Questions regarding the detailed structure of elementary particle physics as well as local quantum gravitational processes are not addressed in this work. The initial goal is to show that essential global properties of the cosmos may potentially be understood from just a few quantum-theoretical principles.

Several of the discussed consequences—particularly those related to black holes, galactic rotation curves, and effective cosmological terms—currently take the form of theoretical interpretations within the AQI framework and require further astrophysical investigation.

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